

Using Twitter to estimate Net Promoter Score (NPS)

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ABSTRACT

Companies invest significant resources to improve and maintain customer loyalty. An effective way to measure customer loyalty is a single-question survey called Net Promoter Score (NPS). Although this survey is valuable for companies who aim to improve or maintain customer loyalty, it can be expensive to administer and can cause survey fatigue for customers. We propose a low-cost estimate for NPS based on Twitter data.

We gathered data from Twitter tweets containing text for three companies: Amazon, Google, and Tesla. After cleaning the tweets, we calculated an AFFIN sentiment score. We labeled tweets as either Promoters or Detractors based on a positive or negative AFFIN score. We used the TF-IDF vectorizer to generate a matrix of features from the tweet corpus. We then trained Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Decision Tree machine learning algorithms to measure a baseline classification accuracy. We then applied hyperparameter tuning to obtain optimal model performance. Logistic regression with hyperparameter tuning performed best with 93.44% accuracy.

The percent of Detractors were then subtracted from the percent of Promoters to calculate an NPS. Our calculated NPS was then compared to the published NPS for the three selected companies. The calculated NPS are consistently higher than published NPS for all three companies analyzed. The results show that

although our results do not perfectly estimate NPS, there is potential for companies to use this method to generate an NPS-like measure more frequently, at a lower cost, and with less intrusion to their customers.

KEYWORDS

NPS, net promoter score, NPS estimator, brand loyalty, customer loyalty, affinity score, machine learning, logistic regression, hyperparameter tuning

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RELATED WORK

Several works have been published addressing customer loyalty measurement and analysis. Ordenes et al. propose a framework for linguistic text-mining for deep analysis of customer experience [1]. Keiningham et al. offer multi-factorial alternatives to NPS that apply correlation and regression analysis to survey data [6]. Seyedhosseini et al. applied cluster analysis to data-mining customer-generated text a single company to assess customer loyalty [7]. Pang and Lee utilized text mining to extract sentimental insights from customer data to improve customer loyalty measurement [8].

These approaches add to the general construct of measurement and deep insight on customer

loyalty. In contrast, our work takes a pragmatic approach. We are not concerned with finding new methods for measuring customer loyalty. Nor are we concerned with extracting deep insight on consumer behavior. Our hypothesis is that we can approximate NPS by using Twitter data.

INTRODUCTION

Studies show that acquiring a new customer is anywhere from five to 25 times more expensive than retaining an existing one [9]. This economics drives companies to invest significant resources to build and maintain customers loyalty. A simple and popular way for companies to measure customer loyalty is Net Promoter Score (NPS). NPS is calculated by surveying customer responses to a single question: “How likely are you to recommend this company to a friend or a colleague?” Customers respond to this question with an integer between 0 and 10; zero being not at all likely recommend and 10 being extremely likely to recommend.

To calculate NPS, start by gathering survey results. Calculate the percent of Promoters defined by responses between 9 and 10. Calculate the percent of Detractors defined by responses between 0 and 6. Subtract the percent of Detractors from the percent of Promoters and this yields the NPS score as shown in Figure 1. NPS is typically represented as an integer rather than a percent (i.e. 40 rather than 40%). NPS scores range from -100 to 100. An NPS of -100 to 0 is generally considered bad, 0 to 50 is good, 50 to 75 is excellent, and 75 to 100 is world class [10].

Figure 1: NPS calculation

We feel it is important to note that the proliferation of the Net Promoter Score as the gold standard for measuring customer loyalty has been challenged many times since it was introduced by Fred Reichheld of Bain & Company in 2003 due to its lack of robustness [2][3][4]. Although we find validity to the criticisms, NPS remains popular with business leaders for its simplicity. NPS has been widely adopted by more than two thirds of Fortune 1000 companies [5].

Our method collects tweets related to the company to estimate NPS. This serves several purposes. First, this reduces the financial cost associated with companies sending out surveys, either in the form of paper surveys or survey software programs. Although free or freemium software is available the collect surveys, many mid to large companies opt to pay for expensive software due to concerns about their information security being compromised. Second, this method is a passive way to collect a loyalty measure from customers. Customer do not have to actively fill out surveys. Data is collected from consumers without contact from the company. Customers are essentially submitting survey-like data when they tweet negative or positive sentiment about companies in tweets. Third, this may reduce the level of survey fatigue that survey respondent can experience. Research shows that administering multiple surveys within a year can significantly suppress response rates in later surveys [13].

METHOD OF STUDY

The steps for our approach are to identify the companies we want to analyze, collect the tweets related to these companies, clean the tweets, apply sentiment analysis to label the tweets as positive (1=Promoter) or negative (0=Detractor). With our preprocessing steps completed, we vectorize the tweet corpus and then apply multiple machine learning algorithms to classify tweets as Promoters or Detractors. We split our data into 75% training data set and 25% test data set. After calculating baseline model accuracy, we perform hyperparameter tuning to improve our accuracy. When our final model is completed, we aggregate the result into as single calculated NPS for each company and compare to the published NPS for that company.

Data Collection and Data Cleaning

We collected tweets containing tweet text for Amazon, Google, and Tesla. We accomplished the collection using the open-source Python library ‘tweepy’ which accesses the Twitter API using our Twitter developer account. We collected 296,107 tweets before cleaning. We cleaned the tweets using the following steps.

(1) We removed unnecessary spaces after # and @.

(2) We removed retweets by filtering tweets that start with ‘RT’.

(3) We removed duplicate tweets based on tweet_id.

(4) We removed tweets that were posted by the company itself. For example, tweets by @Tesla are posted by the Tesla company and were removed.

(5) We removed null strings.

(6) We processed the tweets through ‘tweet-preprocessor’ to clean the tweets. We used the clean method to remove URLs, mentions, reserved words (i.e. RT, FAV), emojis, and smileys.

(7) We dropped empty strings.

(8) We converted all uppercase letters to lowercase.

After cleaning the tweets, 94,796 clean tweets remained for the next step. See Figure 2.

Company	Collected Tweets	Cleaned Tweets
Amazon	120,322	43,230
Google	105,354	32,788
Tesla	70,431	18,778
Total	296,107	94,796

Figure 2: Tweet counts

Sentiment Analysis and Label Encoding

We processed our clean tweets through AFFIN. AFFIN is an open-source Python library performs sentiment analysis on textual data and assigns a sentiment score as a boundless integer. A positive AFFIN score indicates positive sentiments and a negative AFFIN score indicates negative sentiment. Mean and median of AFFIN score was 0 centric. For our labels, we decided to assign AFFIN scores less than zero as 0=Detractors and AFFIN scores greater than or equal to zero as 1=Promoters.

Figure 3: Histogram of AFFIN score (sample)

Machine Learning

With our clean tweets labeled as either Detractors (0) or Promoters (1), we perform our machine learning step. Because computers are good with processing numbers, but not as good with processing textual data, we use TD-IDF to vectorize our tweet corpus to facilitate machine learning. We then split our data in into 75% training data and 25% test data.

We chose multiple classification algorithms to process our clean, labeled, and vectorized tweet corpus. The algorithms selected are Random Forest Classifier, Decision Tree Classifier, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, and Support Vector Classifier (SVC) which is a Support Vector Machine (SVM) method capable of performing binary and multi-class classification. Comparison of different Algorithms was performed using 3-fold cross validation. As seen in Figure 4, the Random Forest Classifier outperformed the others with a mean accuracy of 89.41%. SVC underperformed versus the other algorithms with a mean accuracy of 77.13%. Figure 5 shows a boxplot of the accuracy performance of each algorithm to demonstrate the distributions of accuracy scores.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Description
Random Forest Classifier	0.8941	No Tuning
Decision Tree Classifier	0.8782	No Tuning
Logistic Regression	0.8752	No Tuning
Naive Bayes	0.8655	No Tuning
SVC	0.7713	No Tuning

Figure 4: Baseline accuracy

Although these are subjectively acceptable accuracy scores, we believed that they can be improved using hyperparameter tuning (or hyperparameter optimization). Hyperparameter tuning is the method of adjusting parameters from their default to achieve improved predictive accuracy. To accomplish this, we used the methods from the scikit-learn documentation [11]. By implementing these techniques, we improved our accuracy for several algorithms.

Figure 5: Baseline accuracy boxplot

Note we did not attempt to tune the Decision Tree Classifier as it is closely related to Random Forest and baseline performance was comparable. As seen in Figure 6, there was marginal accuracy improvement from hyperparameter tuning for Naive Bayes and Random Forest. The most impressive improvements occurred for SVC and Logistic Regression. SVC accuracy improved from 77.13% to 92.84%. Logistic Regression accuracy improved from 87.52% to 93.44%. By tuning the Logistic Regression algorithm, its

accuracy surpassed the both baseline and tuned accuracies of the Random Forest Classifier.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Description
Logistic Regression (Tuned)	0.9344	Tuned parameter={ 'C': 10, 'penalty': 'l1' }
SVC (Tuned)	0.9284	Tuned parameter={ 'C': 10, 'gamma': 0.1 }
Random Forest (Tuned)	0.9084	Tuned using Random search CV
Random Forest Classifier	0.8941	No Tuning
Decision Tree Classifier	0.8782	No Tuning
Naive Bayes (Tuned)	0.8780	Naive Bayes model
Logistic Regression	0.8752	No Tuning
Naive Bayes	0.8655	No Tuning
SVC	0.7713	No Tuning

Figure 6: Baseline and Tuned model accuracy

NPS Calculation

Logistic Regression (Tuned) is our working model that will classify tweets as Detractors and Promoters based on the textual data from the tweet. We calculated the percent of Promoters and subtracted the percent of Detractors. This is our calculated NPS from our model. Figure 7 shows the calculated NPS for each of the three selected companies.

Figure 7: Calculated NPS versus Published NPS

Our model-calculated NPS results are higher for Amazon and Google, by 12 and 18 NPS units

respectively, versus published NPS [14][15]. Our calculated NPS for Tesla is much lower, by 42 NPS units [16].

A potential explanation for the difference in our calculated NPS Tesla score versus the published NPS is that Tesla has had significant problems recently [17]. Those that would impact customer loyalty include the Model S recall, Model 3 production delays, and Model 3 quality issues. It is also possible our data collection includes tweets from some of the negative general public relations missteps. These include Elon Musk recorded smoking marijuana, workplace conditions called into question, and a 9% layoff of the workforce. Although these are not related directly to customer loyalty or experiences, they could be tarnishing Tesla's brand. These would explain a lower calculated tweet-based score versus the published NPS. Perhaps eventually the negative press may affect customer opinion and drag the published NPS.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our model is not a perfect estimate of NPS nor is it intended to be a perfect replacement. It is an NPS-like model that provides a simple and timely means of measuring customer loyalty from Twitter tweets. This approach is cost-effective for companies to implement and can provide consistent and timely customer data. Companies may also establish a streaming Twitter API with which to continually monitor this measure. Note that this will require a paid version of the API we used.

As with any model, it is important to understand the limitations. Based on our results for Amazon and Google, our model overestimates NPS versus published NPS. We believe this is because of the treatment of zero value AFFIN scores in preprocessing as indicating positive

sentiment, when this may be sentiment more closely related to the NPS definition of Passives. We believe there is an opportunity to adjust and rescale AFFIN scores to better fit the NPS model; perhaps assuming a distribution of Detractors, Passives, and Promoters.

Future work can also focus on training a model for many more companies rather than the three we selected. Although we trained the model with a significant tweet volume, we have some concern that there may be some overfitting to the companies we selected.

Future work can also focus on identifying true purchasers of the companies' products or services. Our model collects tweets by users that may have an opinion about the company but may not be paying customers. Narrowing the tweet population to true customers, may move the calculated NPS to be closer to published NPS.

Finally, companies that will see the greatest benefit of this work are small to mid-size companies with limited budgets who want a cost-effective way to track customer loyalty or do not want to irritate customers by over-surveying them. Companies of this size may not have the tweet volume to generate a statistically significant calculated NPS from our model. Future work can determine what tweet volume is appropriate for a valid calculation.

TEAM MEMBER CONTRIBUTIONS

Rene Lizarraga proposed the team project concept and Gautam Matkar and Jisha Varghese agree to proceed. Jisha wrote functions to extract the tweets and performed the data collection and cleaned the text. Gautam and Jisha built the machine learning models together. Gautam implemented hyperparameter tuning on the models. Rene wrote the final project document with input from Gautam and Jisha.

All three team members approved the steps to our approach, preprocessing steps, machine learning implementation, and final project submission.

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